

Research

Estimation of Soil Loss and Ranking Priority in Implementing Soil Erosion Control Measures in Sebeya Catchment, Rwanda

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Abstract: Soil erosion is one of the major environmental issues causing the loss of topsoil and fertility in agricultural land. Western part of Rwanda including Sebeya catchment has high susceptibility to erosion leading to huge amounts of soil loss and river sedimentation. The present study held to estimate the actual soil loss from Sebeya catchment and its 8 sub-catchments. ArcGIS software was used to delineate the catchment and its sub-catchments and for mapping all USLE factors. By integrating all maps of USLE factors in GIS, the average soil loss from the whole catchment area was estimated to 130.724 t/ha/yr. Kanzenze sub-catchment was found to be the 1st sub-catchment alarming the intervention with a soil loss of 243.868 t/ha/yr while Bitenga sub-catchment appears at the last rank with a soil loss of 86.922 t/ha/yr for this prioritization in implementing soil erosion control measures. Therefore, the unevenly spatial distribution of soil erosion rates in this study should help the agricultural managers to improve their strategy in planning and implementing the soil erosion control measures in Sebeya catchment.

Keywords: Soil loss estimation, Sebeya catchment, Rwanda

1. Introduction

Soil erosion is regarded as one of the major causes of soil degradation that affect the productive capacity of agriculture and terrestrial ecosystems (Chen et al., 2019). High susceptibility to erosion lead to huge amounts of soil loss and river sedimentation.

Worldwide, erosion on cropland averages about $30 \text{ t}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}\cdot\text{yr}^{-1}$ and ranges from 0.5 to 400 $\text{t}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}\cdot\text{yr}^{-1}$ (Stanchi et al., 2015) while in Rwanda, the soil erosion rate was estimated at 250 $\text{t}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}\cdot\text{yr}^{-1}$ (Karamage et al., 2016). Moreover, FAO classified about 40% of Rwanda's land having a very high erosion risk, and another 37% requires soil retention measures before cultivation, the only 23% of the cultivated land are under free or less of soil erosion risk (Munyaneza , 2013).

Located in the Western Province of Rwanda, Sebeya catchment is of high vulnerability to soil erosion due to various factors such as abundant rainfall, hilly and mountainous relief, demographic pressure and agricultural expansion on steep slope terrain (IWRM, 2018; MoE, 2018). Green agriculture and improved mining are promoted and supported through different practices, but there are still several cases of unsustainable mining and agriculture leading to high accelerated erosion and terrible river sedimentation in this catchment during heavy rainfall (IWRM, 2018).

This research held to firstly estimate soil loss using Universal Soil Loss Equation (USLE) with GIS applications and finally to find appropriate criteria for ranking priority in implementing soil erosion control measures in Sebeya catchment. Quantitative information on soil erosion rates help in monitoring and assessing the environmental impacts of soil erosion and in making the management strategies.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

The study area of this research is focused on Sebeya catchment located in the Western Province of Rwanda and shared by four administrative units namely Rubavu, Nyabihu, Rutsiro and Ngororero Districts (Figure1). Sebeya catchment is located in the high elevation region of the country with altitude varying between 1,462 m to 2,979 m a.b.s.l. (meters above sea level). This catchment is also characterised by steep slopes and abundant rainfall varying between 1,200 mm to 1,700 mm per year (Birdlife international, 2018) revealing that a great part of this catchment falls in medium risk to very high risk of erosion according to the classification of MoE in 2018.

Figure 1. Sebeya catchment location

2.2. Data collection

Literature review, site visits and informal interviews were used to get sufficient information on the actual status of soil erosion and its control measures in Sebeya catchment. The input data include Digital Elevation Model (DEM), soil data, rainfall data, hydrological data and land use / land cover data were collected from the Center of Geographical Information System of University of Rwanda (CGIS UR).

2.2.1. Catchment and sub-catchment delineation

Catchment delineation is a technique that involves a series of steps which requires various data such as Districts boundaries, Rwanda rivers and the DEM of those Districts to be available. To delineate each sub-catchment, the pourpoint was created at the outlet of each Sebeya river tributary.

2.2.2. The Universal Soil Loss Equation (USLE)

Proposed by Wischmeier and Smith in 1978, the USLE is applied in many areas worldwide and it is described by the following equation:

$$A=R*K*LS*C*P \quad (\text{Eq.1})$$

Where the involved parameters are:

Average annual soil loss A(t/ha*yr); Soil erodibility or K-factor (t^*ha^*hr/ha^*MJ^*mm); Rainfall erosivity or R-factor (MJ^*mm/ha^*hr^*yr); Slope length factor or LS- factor (Dimensionless); Crop management factor or C-factor (Dimensionless); Erosion-control practice factor or P-factor (Dimensionless). With applications in GIS, the equation (Eq.1) was used to estimate the soil loss in Sebeya catchment and its sub-catchment.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Generation of rainfall erosivity factor map

R-factor is the long term annual average of the product of rainfall kinetic energy (KE) in $MJ.ha^{-1}$ and the maximum rainfall intensity in 30 minutes (I_{30}) in $mm.hr^{-1}$ (Zhou et al., 2006). The rainfall factor can vary from year to year, so an average over a number of years is usually used (Ffolliott et al., 2013).

In this study, the obtained precipitation from Rwanda Meteorological Agency is ranging from 1188.089 to 1536.943 mm. Many researchers have proposed the Eq.2 and the use of the raster calculator tool in GIS to compute rainfall erosivity (Narayana and Babu, 1983).

$$R = 81.5+38 \times P \quad (\text{Eq.2})$$

Where R is the rainfall erosivity in $MJ.mm/hr/yr$ and P the point rainfall in mm. The estimated rainfall erosivity ranged from 532.974 to 665.538 $MJ.mm. ha/hr/yr$ (Figure 2) with an average value of 585.15 $MJ.mm.ha/hr/yr$.

Figure 2. R-factor map of sebeya catchment

3.2. Generation of soil erodibility factor map

The soil erodibility factor (K) indicates the susceptibility of soil to erosion where it reflects the effect of soil properties and soil profile characteristics on soil loss (Renard et al., 1997). From literature, different researchers have identified the variability of the soil erodibility values with the soil texture (Table 1). The soil erodibility factor is determined by soil texture and organic matter content (DeVere, 1997).

Table 1. Soil texture and soil erodibility factor

SN	Texture	K_factor	References
1	Silt loam	0.450	(David, 1988)
2	Loam	0.300	(Oruk et al. 2012)
3	Clay	0.225	(Oruk et al. 2012)
4	Clay 25-35%	0.760	(Belasri et al. 2017)
5	Sandy clay loam	0.200	(Oruk et al. 2012)
6	Sandy loam	0.233	(Chaudhary and Kumar, 2018)

7	Silty clay	0.350	(Dymond, 2010)
8	Clay loam	0.305	(Oruk et al. 2012)
9	Sandy clay	0.200	(David, 1988)

The K-factor map (Figure 3) was obtained from the K-factors shown in Table 1 with GIS applications. The soil erodibility factor of Sebeya catchment varies from 0.2 to 0.76 t.ha.hr⁻¹. ha⁻¹MJ⁻¹ (Figure 3) with an average value of 0.384 t.ha.hr⁻¹. ha⁻¹MJ⁻¹.

Figure 3. K-factor map of Sebeya catchment

3.3. Generation of the topographic factor map

The topographic factor **LS** is defined as the ratio of soil loss under the given conditions to that at the site with the “standard” slope steepness of 9% and the slope length of 22.13m (Ganasri and Ramesh, 2015).

This study used the Eq.3 for computation of LS based on the upslope contributing area suggested by (Desmet and Govers, 1996; Hrabalíková and Janeček, 2015; Simms et al. 2003).

$$LS = (As/22.13)^m (\sin \beta / 0.0896)^n \quad (\text{Eq.3})$$

Where **As** is the up slope contributing area per unit width (m), β is the steepest slope angle (radian) and m and n are slope length exponent and slope steepness exponent, respectively. For rill flow, the values of exponents are m = 0.6 and n = 1.3. LS-factors of Sebeya catchment were calculated using (Eq.3) with GIS applications. The results vary from 0 to 470.882 as shown in Figure 4 with an average value of 5.737 (Dimensionless).

Figure 4. LS-factor map of Sebeya catchment

3.4. Generation of the cropping-management factor map

In USLE-types equation, the value of C-Factor includes the effects of crop cover, crop sequence, length of growing season, tillage practices, residue management and the expected time distribution of erosive rainstorms (DeVere, 1997).

From the collected Land cover land use data of Sebeya catchment, GIS was used to determine C-factor map and it ranges from 0.008 to 0.34 (Table 2 and Figure 5) with an average value of 0.303 (Dimensionless).

Table 2. C-factor of different land cover

SN	LCLU	C_factor	References
1	Forest plantation	0.020	Kumar and kushwaha, (2013)
2	Built-up area	0.200	(Devatha et al., 2013; David, 1988)
3	Closed agriculture	0.340	(Devatha et al., 2015)
4	Irrigation	0.340	(Devatha et al., 2015)
5	Natural forest	0.008	(Kumar and kushwaha, 2013)
6	Open land	0.340	(Devatha et al., 2015)
7	Open agriculture	0.340	(Devatha et al., 2015)

Figure 5. C-factor map of Sebeya catchment

3.5. Generation of the control practice factor map

The P-factor represents the effect of various support practices such as contour farming, terracing and strip cropping for arresting soil erosion being taken up in the area (Chaudhary and Kumar, 2019; Panagos et al. 2015). P-factor map (Figure 6) was prepared on the basis of land use-land cover P-factors presented in Table 3. The P-factor value for Sebeya catchment is ranging from 0.001 to 0.5 as shown in Figure 6 with an average value of 0.333 (Dimensionless).

Table 3. P- factors of different land cover / land use

SN	Land cover type	P-factor	References
1	Built-up area	0.300	(Kumar and Kushwaha, 2013)
2	Closed agriculture	0.500	(Kumar and Kushwaha, 2013)
3	Forest plantation	0.001	(Lu et al. 2010)
4	Irrigation	0.500	(Kumar and Kushwaha, 2013)
5	Natural forest	0.001	(Lu et al. 2010)
6	Open agriculture	0.500	(Kumar and Kushwaha, 2013)
7	Open land	0.020	(Molla and Sisheber, 2016)

Figure 6. P-factor map of Sebeya catchment

3.6. Integration of USLE parameters in GIS

The average annual soil erosion rate (A) is computed by multiplying the average USLE parameters estimated in the previous sections of results (Eq.1). Using the classification proposed by MoE in 2018, the final soil loss map has grouped the soil erosion rates into 6 ranges (very low, low, Moderate, high, very high and extremely high erosion) as shown in Figure 7 and Table 4 with a mean annual soil erosion rate of 130.724 t/ha/yr. The same soil erosion rate is obtained by multiplying the 5 average USLE parameters previously estimated.

Table 4. Soil erosion estimation in Sebeya catchment

SN	Soil loss ranges (t/ha/yr)	Soil erosion classification (MoE, 2018)	Average soil loss (t/ha/yr)	covered area (km ²)	Weighted area (t/ha/yr)*km ²	Average soil loss (t/ha/yr)
1	0-5	Very low	2.5	199.372	498.4300	130.7243
2	5-10	Low	7.5	15.495	116.2192	
3	10-25	moderate	22.5	20.913	470.545	
4	25-50	high	37.5	13.474	505.2845	
5	50-100	Very high	75	18.635	1397.674	
6	>100	Extremely high	466.429	95.416	44504.948	
	Total			363.307	47493.102	

Figure 7. Soil erosion potential in Sebeya catchment

3.7. Ranking priority in sub-catchments of Sebeya catchment

This research has divided Sebeya catchment into 8 sub-catchments which were delineated based on the flow accumulation at different pourpoints of the existing tributaries in this catchment (Figure 8).

Figure 8. The eight sub-catchments of Sebeya catchment

By considering the cumulative amount of soil loss per year in each agricultural area enclosed by each sub-catchment as a ranking criteria, Kanzenze sub-catchment seems to be the 1st sub-catchment alarming the intervention with a soil loss of 243.868 t/ha/yr and a cumulative annual soil loss of 1.439 million t/yr while Bikeneke sub-catchment does not require immediate intervention because its soil loss falls below the maximum soil loss tolerance value of 11.5 t/ha/yr (Bagarello, 2015). The Table 5 shows various proposed sequences for this prioritization of implementing soil erosion control measures in Sebeya catchment.

Table 5. Ranking priority in implementing soil erosion control measures in Sebeya sub-catchments

SN	Sub-catchment	Area (ha)	Soil loss (t/ha/yr)	area of arable land (ha)	Soil loss from arable area (t/yr)	Ranking
1	Kanzenze	6468.2	243.868	5900.290	1438892.106	1
2	Pfunda	6030.4	87.102	4752.733	413972.587	5
3	Karambo	3100.1	198.325	2757.848	546950.312	3
4	Bihongoro	4163	127.192	3493.778	444380.492	4
5	Gatare	2037.9	65.339	2038.104	133167.680	6

6	Bitenga	1488.1	86.922	1371.048	119174.238	7
7	Bikeneko	998.3	2.362	821.967	1941.486	8
8	Sebeya corridor	12045	102.74	10599.572	1089000.040	2
	TOTAL	36331		31735.341	4187478.941	

4. Conclusions and recommendations

Soil erosion potential within Sebeya catchment was addressed in order to quantify soil erosion rates for better planning of soil conservation and sustainable agriculture. Characterized by steep slopes and abundant rainfall, Sebeya catchment falls in medium risk to very high risk of erosion with an estimated annual soil loss of 130.724 t/ha/yr.

In this study, Sebeya catchment was delineated into 8 sub-catchments based on Sebeya river tributaries and the analysis of the spatial distribution of soil loss throughout the entire catchment revealed high vulnerability to soil erosion in Kanzenze sub-catchment with high erosion rate estimated at 243.868 t/ha/yr.

Finally, the methodology developed in this research should help agriculture managers in the process of ranking priority for implementing soil erosion control measures in the catchment.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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